

THE LEADERSHIP'S BEHAVIOUR ON INSTITUTIONAL TRANSFORMATION OF A PREVIOUSLY DISADVANTAGED HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA.

Khotso Keletso Moikanyane

Department of Development Planning and Management, University of Limpopo, Private Bag X1106, Sovenga, 0727, South Africa, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5403-7739>

Abstract

Institutional transformation is a complex process that necessitates meticulous planning and management. As a result, it is imperative that an institution establishes effective leadership that will best steer the institution toward the desired objectives. Higher education and training is one sector that identified the need for transformation of its public tertiary institutions because of historical inequalities and imbalances, particularly with historically disadvantaged institutions. Universities are viewed as a driving force for social, political, and economic transformation. The state government's transition to a democratic regime shaped policies and took into account components of global trends. This magnitude prompted research on the behaviour and perspective of leadership on institutional transformation of a historically disadvantaged institution (HDU). The University of Limpopo as one of the institutions in South Africa that is categorised under the previously disadvantaged was used as a case study for this research. The study used an exploratory sequential mixed-method approach that relied equally on primary and secondary data collection. Questionnaires, interviews, document analysis, and past publications were used to collect data that contributed to the study's conclusions. The findings of the study clearly show that effective leadership is a key factor in attaining the institution's transformational goals. The conclusions revealed that the institution's leadership should adopt a full transformational style of leadership qualities to ensure effective institutional transformation. This will provide the institution with greater opportunities and broaden its impact on society.

Keywords: *Leadership, Institutional Transformation, Historically Disadvantaged Institution and Higher Education*

1. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Leadership is critical in institutional restructuring (Susanto & Sawitri, 2022; Moikanyane, 2021). There is a widely held belief that an effective leadership approach is critical to solving the issues of previously disadvantaged institutions (Mouton, Louw & Strydom, 2013; Chipunza & Gwarinda, 2010). To that degree, modifications in institutional structures were observed, as well as improvements in university quality (Govinder, Zondo & Makgoba, 2013). These shifts occurred as a result of political and economic variations fueled by global trends. The universal acceptance of leadership transformation as a driver of mergers of historically disadvantaged universities has resulted in the majority of developing-country states attempting to address the imbalance within social systems (Enemuo, 2019; Mzangwa, 2019; Tsheola & Nembambula, 2015). Pressure on governments to evolve to handle socioeconomic and political change influenced state institutions to consider reforming several sectors, including higher education (Lange, 2020; Shackleton, Riordan & Simonis, 2006). Following the demise of the colonial administration, a significant number of African states invested in education in the hope of addressing socioeconomic challenges, emphasising the importance of formal education in the socioeconomic liberation of societies (Enemuo, 2019; Makgamatha & Moikanyane, 2018; United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), 2015; Otieno, 2013).

The study emphasises on the importance of leadership behaviour in South African institutional transformation. The focus is on the transition of these institutions from apartheid to the current democratic regime (Mzangwa, 2019). Because of the old government's leadership style, South African institutions were characterised by a variety of inequalities and imbalances (Rensburg, 2020; Govinder, et al., 2013; Mouton, et al., 2013). As a result, the new democratic government formulated measures to transform the higher education landscape, which led to the establishment of the National Commission on Higher Education (NCHE) (Lange, 2020; Connell, 2019; Mouton, et al., 2013). The aim was to address issues of race, gender, and cultural disparities that emerged as a result of apartheid driven institutions (Tyson, Orphan, Kiyama & Nelson, 2020; Shackleton, et al., 2006; Cloete & Moja, 2005).

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Theories exist to define and explain a natural phenomenon. They are designed to provide an understanding of a natural phenomenon based on an observation and approximated empirical data (Male & Palaologou, 2019; Nawaz & Khan, 2016). They also serve as a framework for researchers to organise existing knowledge in order to provide comprehensive explanations and evidence for how constructs are related in order to draw inferences from the findings (Ly, 2020). It is therefore significant to have background knowledge on the practices of leadership in the context of institutional transformation.

The role of leadership in the transformation of institutions and organisations has evolved and been revised to the extent where new theories and approaches are being proposed all the time (Nawaz & Khan, 2016). Since the need for leaders to transform institutions arose, there has been debates and discussions on the appropriate leadership theory for institutional transformation (McPhail, 2019). Researchers can discover the common qualities and behavioural patterns that create effective leadership by analysing the leadership theory (McCaffery, 2018). The leadership style outlines how a leader leads team members based on their leadership and managerial qualities (Ford & Harding, 2018). The rationale is that while both leadership and management principles are required for leading an institution, the concept of a leadership approach is much more important for an institution dealing with change and going through a transformational process (McCaffery, 2018; Willis, Clarke & O'Connor, 2017).

The premise is that transformation can only be successful if appropriate leadership qualities are used rather than simply depending on a managerial approach (Hiller & Beauchesne, 2014). It should also be noted that there are several types of leadership; hence, it is essential to know the type of leadership approach that will be most effective in dealing with the transformation (Susanto & Sawitri, 2022; Willis, et al., 2017). According to the literature, different leadership styles have been evaluated and investigated in terms of which approach is best suited to managing change, and data demonstrates that many authors emphasise the transformational leadership theory (Dinh, Caliskan & Zhu 2020).

Transformational leadership theory is considered one of the most effective approaches that leaders need to adopt for addressing change and transformation in an institution (Cho, Shin, Billing & Bhagat, 2019; Aithal, 2015). The significance of the theory is that it focuses entirely on dealing with transformation, which is the basis of this study. According to Burns (1978), the introduction of the theory of transformational leadership came as an approach for political leaders and has been broadened for use in organisational psychology. Transformational leadership is regarded as an approach for leadership that aims at bringing change to an individual, group, organisation as well as social system (Clarke, 2018; Bass, 1985; Burns, 1978). The theory aims at trying to bring positive change in the system and structure of something (Chipunza & Gwarinda, 2010; Bass & Avolio, 1993).

An author named James MacGregor Burns in the 1970s introduced the complete conceptual phase of transformational leadership and was further extended by Bernard Bass in the 1980s, since then the theory has been used as an approach for institutional transformation (Clarke, 2018; Bass & Avolio, 1993). The conceptualisation of the theory demonstrated that a transformational leader emphasises the following factors, which include idealised influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individual consideration (Govinder, et al., 2013; Chipunza & Gwarinda, 2010; Burns, 1978). The theory on leadership demonstrates the idea that leadership is beyond what we do when placed in a position of power to steer an institution, but rather what everyone follows when we express sincerely the deepest thoughts, ideas and feelings when performing our duties (Ndebele, 2007). The inclusivity of passion and integrity in what we do; understanding that whatever it is that is done is not of the thought of a promised reward afterwards but the overwhelming thought and sense of appropriateness that it needs to be done.

Studies on leadership have identified that the most vital leadership requirements lean towards transformational factors that assist towards institutional restructuring (Berg & Jarbur, 2014; Dinh, et al., 2014). This is with the assumption that institutions will at some point in their lifespan, have to go through a process of restructuring and changing. Society and its methods of doing things will forever change, therefore it is important to have leadership in the changing environment that can adapt and manage a process of change.

3. TYPES AND VALUES OF LEADERSHIP

Multiple styles of leadership are adopted to create change in a group, organisation or institution (Susanto & Sawitri 2022; Northouse, 2018; Mohuba & Govender, 2016). These forms of leadership may include autocratic, participative, laissez-faire, transactional and transformational leadership among others; hence, leadership can constitute more than one style of leadership at the same time such as transactional leadership and transformational leadership (Adserias, Charleston & Jackson, 2017; Nawaz & Khan, 2016). According to the path-goal theory, which emphasises the idea that if a leader can analyse a situation based on what is required by the

subordinates or the industry, they can be able to change their style of leadership and adapt to the most suitable one for the situation (Farhan, 2018; Phillips & Phillips, 2016; House, 1996). For example, if the situation requires a leader to be autocratic at some point and supportive at another point, the leadership should be flexible and change their style as required. The type of leadership approach should correspond with the objectives of an institution (Moikanyane, 2021).

The purpose of transformation is to create positive change to the conditions of individuals and organisations either to enhance performance or to overcome challenges (Mohuba & Govender, 2016; Myatt, 2013). The transformation of the historically disadvantaged universities requires a leadership approach that is effective and capable of meeting the goals and objectives of the predetermined vision of the institution (Mohuba & Govender, 2016; Aithal, 2015; Vinger & Cilliers, 2006). The logic is that leadership comes in many different forms and each form is created for a specific situation, meaning that one form of leadership might not work in some situations and some might (Karodia, Shaikh & Soni, 2015; Myatt, 2013; Randall & Coakley, 2007). There is a need to first understand the ideas and vision of followers to establish the most effective leadership approach.

The definition of leadership in academia is defined similarly to the leadership in the business environs (Moikanyane, 2021). It involves qualities of being a visionary, having the ability to plan by being proactive to situations but at the same time also having the ability to be reactive to situations and come up with responsive measures (Braun, Peus, Frey, & Knipfer, 2016; Berg & Jarbur, 2014). Leadership emphasises being a role model, inspiring others, being self-aware and selfreflective (Antonakis & Day, 2018). In summary, leadership is referred to the ability to ensure the success of other people who follow (Ford & Harding, 2018). Additionally, some universities state the need to lead others in the different departments and sections within the institution such as teaching and learning, research, community engagement, innovating and dissemination of ideas within a tight framework and competitive setting (CHE, 2016b; Berg & Jarbur, 2014). The notion of academic leadership is discussed at the universities, with an expressed need to define it clearly.

Universities in particular are institutions of higher learning constituting mostly academics in multiple fields to acquire knowledge to improve their well-being and society (Kromydas, 2017; Hancock & Nuttman, 2014; Cloete & Moja, 2005). The discussion on academic leadership needs to be clarified, hence universities argue on that notion to clarify the definition of leadership in academia (Johnston, 2019; Braun, et al., 2016). The difficulty in clearly defining leadership in academia lies in the lack of strategies that describe where they want the universities to be in the future from a general perspective (Connell, 2019; Vinger & Cilliers, 2006). If that issue is addressed, then we can define the kind of leadership that will be able to help achieve the vision of the institution.

There is a need for the adoption of different leadership approaches, especially in institutions that are going through a transformational change (Susanto & Sawitri, 2022; Moikanyane, 2021). This includes institutions in the higher education sector (Strielkowski & Chigisheva, 2018). The leadership approach should encourage academic professionals to actively participate in effective reframing and rebuilding the changing social covenant of the academy (Gravett, Kinchin & Winstone, 2020; Wergin, 2007). A collegial model should be adopted if institutions need to effectively succeed with the changing environment of the social structures. A neo-collegial model that emphasises the addition of a modern twist that allows the academic leadership and other academic professionals to engage in the life of the institutions while forswearing the cordial and insularity of the past (Rehbock, 2020; Antonakis & Day, 2018; Wergin, 2007). This model is rather not new but a redefined model that emphasises “a shift in attitude about leaders and leadership – from a hierarchical view that academic leadership flows from a leadership position to a much more lateral view those leadership roles are available to everyone” (Wergin, 2007: 12).

4. INSTITUTIONAL TRANSFORMATION

Societal and institutional transformation is not an automatic process that is free of intervention (Laursen, & De Welde, 2019). There could be a variety of complex factors that could precipitate and agitate for transformation. Institutions across the world are structured based on various characteristics and systems (Afolabi & Omal, 2020). They exist to help improve the quality of life of people (Kromydas, 2017). Certain factors shape the operation and outcomes of these institutions. According to Tsheola & Nembambula (2015:22), they are considered as “social systems that consist of different personalities and characters, including those that may seek to halt and disrupt progress, be destructive without knowing it, complaining about selfcreated problems, cause division and conflict, deluding themselves of roles and the perfectly honest, genuine and committed stakeholders”. The struggling and marginalized institutions were required to undergo reshaping their systems, due to political controversies, ineffective strategies and structural inefficiencies (Mohuba & Govender, 2016; Karodia, et al., 2015). Institutions are the mirrors of societal change, whereby when excessive racism, sexism or any form of discrimination and

imbalances seem to exist (Tyson, et al., 2020; Mzangwa, 2019). It does not only affect the universities leadership but the whole of society in general (Kromydas, 2017; Karodia, et al., 2015; Govinder, et al., 2013).

There are varieties of factors that may constitute failures in the transformational process of institutions. This may include the lack of sufficient resources, be it time, finance, skills and knowledge that will act as a constraint to the accomplishment of the goals and objectives of institutional transformation (Afolabi & Omal, 2020; Liu, 2016). The reasons for institutional transformation in South Africa have a resemblance with the history of the country (Rensburg, 2020). Societal institutions are recognised as a strategic approach to societal change through their principles, practices and processes (Sadik, Marouf & Khaleel, 2020; Tyson, et al., 2020). Institutional transformation requires a process of effective management by the leadership. There is a distinction between leadership and management, which the heads of institutions need to understand and integrate. A major challenge in institutional restructuring is when leaders have difficulties incorporating and merging leadership with management (CHE, 2016a).

5. METHODOLOGY

To acquire the most relevant data to answer the research question, the study used an exploratory sequential mixed-method approach that included both qualitative and quantitative methodology. A normative research design was adopted to collect data, which took the form of a simple survey-based study and field research. Participants' information was gathered using questionnaires and interviews. The researcher used both primary and secondary data to interpret theoretical and practical data through background information and current information.

The University of Limpopo (UL), which is one of South Africa's previously disadvantaged institution, was chosen as the focus area for the research study. The research study identified the target population as the University of Limpopo's top leadership (executive management) and the Student Representative Council (SRC). The sample size consisted of the institution's top 14 influential executives and 1 SRC. The key participants were drawn from the top executive leadership structure of the institution, which includes individuals with substantial executive powers inside the institution. Ethical clearance was obtain from the Turfloop Research Ethics Committee (TREC) to carry out the study.

A non-probability sampling method was applied, with a purposive sampling procedure used to select the key informants. Questionnaires were distributed to participants. To collect the primary data, a Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) was employed, as well as a prearranged interview. Secondary data was also used by the researcher, which included document analysis (reports) and a review of literature written by other scholars, disciplines, and institutions.

The qualitative data analysis involved thorough content analysis by the researcher to interpret the data collected from literature as well as discussions and responses of participants. Quantitative data analysis technique involved descriptive statistics and graphical displays using tables. Graphs and charts were created using Microsoft Excel. The validity of the study was confirmed by replicating the survey and interview structure with each interview. Triangulation with annual reports, press articles and additional sources further supported the internal validity of the study. Reliability was assured through an accurate research instrument test on a trial respondent before the surveys and interviews. A research instrument (MLQ) that is widely approved to measure leadership style and behaviour was used to provide accurate information.

4. RESULTS

Leadership behaviour

A close-ended questionnaire was distributed to respondents to determine how frequently each of the following assertions best suits them in order to understand the type and style of leadership approach that university leaders have adopted. The table and statements below determine the university's leadership behaviour and style.

Table 1: Leadership's behaviour

Statements	Not at all	Once in a while	Sometimes	Fairly Often	Frequently, if not always	Total
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<i>I make others feel good to be around</i>	Count (%)	0	0	0	3 (30%)	7 (70%)	10 (100%)
<i>I express with a few simple words what we could and should do</i>	Count (%)	0	1 (10%)	2 (20%)	6 (60%)	1 (10%)	10 (100%)
<i>I enable others to think about old problems in new ways</i>	Count (%)	0	0	3 (30%)	6 (60%)	1 (10%)	10 (100%)
<i>I help others develop themselves</i>	Count (%)	0	0	1 (10%)	7 (70%)	2 (20%)	10 (100%)
<i>I tell others what to do if they want to be rewarded for their work.</i>	Count (%)	0	0	1 (10%)	7 (70%)	2 (20%)	10 (100%)
<i>I am satisfied when others meet agreed-upon standards</i>	Count (%)	0	0	0	0	10 (100%)	10 (100%)
<i>I am content to let others continue working in the same ways always</i>	Count (%)	1 (10%)	7 (70%)	1 (10%)	0	1 (10%)	10 (100%)
<i>Others have complete faith in me</i>	Count (%)	0	0	1 (10%)	8 (80%)	1 (10%)	10 (100%)
<i>I provide appealing images about what we can do</i>	Count (%)	0	0	2 (20%)	6 (60%)	2 (20%)	10 (100%)
<i>I provide others with new ways of looking at puzzling things.</i>	Count (%)	0	0	3 (30%)	5 (50%)	2 (20%)	10 (100%)
<i>I let others know how I think they are doing.</i>	Count (%)	0	0	0	7 (70%)	3 (30%)	10 (100%)
<i>I provide recognition/rewards when others reach their goals</i>	Count (%)	0	0	3 (30%)	6 (60%)	1 (10%)	10 (100%)
<i>As long as things are working, I do not try to change anything.</i>	Count (%)	0	0	3 (30%)	6 (60%)	1 (10%)	10 (100%)
<i>Whatever others want to do is OK with me</i>	Count (%)	2 (20%)	5 (50%)	1 (10%)	2 (20%)	0	10 (100%)
<i>Others are proud to be associated with me.</i>	Count (%)	2 (20%)	5 (50%)	1 (10%)	2 (20%)	0	10 (100%)

<i>I help others find meaning in their work.</i>	Count (%)	3 (30%)	5 (50%)	2 (20%)	0	0	10 (100%)
	Count (%)	0	0	1 (10%)	8 (80%)	1 (10%)	10 (100%)
	Count (%)	0	0	1 (10%)	7 (70%)	2 (20%)	10 (100%)
<i>I get others to rethink ideas that they had never questioned before.</i>	Count (%)	0	0	3 (30%)	6 (60%)	1 (10%)	10 (100%)
	Count (%)	0	0	1 (10%)	8 (80%)	1 (10%)	10 (100%)
<i>I give personal attention to others who seem rejected</i>	Count (%)	0	0	1 (10%)	6 (60%)	3 (30%)	10 (100%)
<i>I call attention to what others can get for what they accomplish</i>	Count (%)	0	0	0	3 (30%)	7 (70%)	10 (100%)
<i>I tell others the standards they have to know to carry out their work.</i>	Count (%)	1 (10%)	2 (20%)	5 (50%)	1 (10%)	1 (10%)	10 (100%)
<i>I ask no more of others than what is absolutely essential</i>	Count (%)	1 (10%)	2 (20%)	5 (50%)	1 (10%)	1 (10%)	10 (100%)

The assertions are based on constructs that define various leadership behaviours and approaches. The study included 14 top executive leadership personnel from the university and the SRC (1) but only 10 of the 15 participants were able to participate in the survey. The questionnaire prompted participants to indicate how frequently they related to and/or practise each of the above statements. One hundred percent (100%) of the 10 respondents successfully answered all of the statements. Twenty-one statements were written, and each participant had to choose how frequently each statement defined their leadership from a five-point scale. The scale options included "not at all," "once in a while," "sometimes," "fairly often," and "frequently, if not always."

In relation to the above statements, the participants barely chose the option of 'not at all,' while the average answers were on the option of 'fairly often.' However, the data show that all participants are "satisfied when others meet agreed upon standards" "frequently, if not always." This emphasises the idea that most of the university's executives (leadership) have a mutual understanding that subordinates must satisfy the agreed-upon standards. This is consistent with the second last statement, in which all of the executives "fairly often" (3 participants) and "frequently, if not always" (7 participants), "tell others the standards they have to know to carry out their work". This helps subordinates to better understand how to carry out their duties and meet the objectives of their departments and institution.

Factors for measuring the leadership style

The MLQ measures participants' leadership based on specific factors related to the institution's leadership approach. The table below shows the scores for each individual factor that describes the leadership style. The measurement was derived from the table under "Leadership Behaviour." The questionnaire table was created considering leadership constructs.

Table 2: Leadership style factors

Factors	Description
1. Idealised Influence	Indicates whether you hold subordinates' trust, maintain their faith and respect, show dedication to them, appeal to their hopes and dreams, and act as their role model.
2. Inspirational Motivation	Measures the degree to which you provide a vision, use appropriate symbols and images to help others focus on their work, and try to make others feel their work is significant.
3. Intellectual Stimulation	Shows the degree to which you encourage others to be creative in looking at old problems in new ways, create an environment that is tolerant of seemingly extreme positions, and nurture people to question their own values and beliefs of those of the organisation.
4. Individualised Consideration	Indicates the degree to which you show interest in others' well-being, assign projects individually, and pay attention to those who seem less involved in the group.
5. Contingent Reward	Shows the degree to which you tell others what to do to be rewarded, emphasise what you expect from them, and recognise their accomplishments.
6. Management-By-Exception	Assesses whether you tell others the job requirements, are content with the standard performance, and believe in the idea that if something is not broken then there is no need to fix anything.
7. Laissez-Faire	Measures whether you require little of others are content to let things ride, and let others do their own thing.

Figure 1: Scoring factors for leadership measurement

Two types of leadership behaviours stood out: transformational and transactional. The graph shows that all of the factors that constitute transactional leadership have a score of 90 or higher, including the aspects of

'management-by-exception' and 'contingent reward.' Two of the four transformational leadership elements, namely 'individual consideration' and 'idealised influence,' have also received a score of 90 or higher. A score of 90 or higher indicates that the leadership is exceptional in those areas and that the majority of the institution's leadership exercises those leadership aspects.

The responses were exhibited 'fairly often' on average for the following behaviours: inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, idealised influence, individual consideration, contingent reward and management by exception. However, the construct of idealised influence had the highest score of 97. This emphasises the idea that the leadership are highly respected and trusted by their followers for what they do. The 'idealised influence' is an aspect of a transformational style of leadership. The construct of laissez-faire achieved the lowest score of 41 amongst all factors. The idea emphasises a leadership who cares less about what others do and does not encourage working together. Hence, that is the reason why both factors of 'Inspirational motivation' and 'Intellectual stimulation' received a score of between 80 and 90, which is considered the average score. This means that the majority, if not all of the executives epitomise those two factors 'fairly often' towards their subordinates.

Role of a leader

The general points that the participants' highlighted to be the role of a leader was that a leader needs to provide direction, support and initiative in activities, projects and initiatives linked to the university. To resolve challenges arising out of the different areas that are under their portfolios. To support staff and students so that the institution can improve its teaching and learning, and research profile continually. Lastly, to give strategic direction on various goals of the institution.

Leadership strengths and weaknesses

Majority (60%) of the executive leadership remarked that one of their greatest strengths is their interpersonal skills. The ability to connect with people, specifically with the students and staff. Some other participants highlighted on their creative and innovative capabilities to improve their departments and organisation.

The general weaknesses that prevailed from the participants is that some leaders lack the ability to become strict towards their subordinates and are too considerate to other. Other leaders emphasised on the fact that they tend to over work themselves and always try to push at all costs. Some other leaders are perfectionist therefore; they tend to do the work themselves rather than delegating to ensure optimum results.

Management of institutional transformation

The executive leadership stated that one of the most significant aspects of managing an institution in a transformational phase, such as a previously disadvantaged university, is to have a leadership that serves the institution for at least a 5-year period. This is owing to the fact that changing leadership has a negative impact on the university's system. This is simply because, in order to comprehend the institutional transformation process, you must be present from the start and monitor the process throughout to ensure that what was planned is carried out.

5. DISCUSSION

The top leadership is responsible for serving on the executive management committee and influencing executive decisions in order to guide the institution through the transformation process toward the predetermined vision. The university, over the past years has been going through a transformational phase. Different leadership approaches prevailed and the institutional transformation process has had its pros and cons. The leadership has had a great deal of an effect in the transformation of the institution. In the executive leadership of the institution, a blend of three types of leadership approaches prevailed, including transactional, transformational, and autocratic leadership, however the qualities of a transformational approach dominated. According to the study, a good leader is somebody who knows the ins and outs of their institution, which includes departments, staff, students, and everything else that is a part of the university. The leaders are focused on providing direction, support, and launching initiatives that provide a clear vision for their respective departments as well as the institution as a whole. Their goal is to provide strategic direction and guidance on various university goals, as well as to boost morale.

The notion of academic freedom for the staff of the university is very important to create a good relationship between the leadership and the staff members. This includes respecting an individual's rights and opportunity to express themselves, even if they disagree with them. It is sickening to experience instances in which some people are mistreated based on disciplinary hearings at times within the university. The institution is more likely to undergo a positive transformation if the leadership shifts from an autocratic style of leadership to a more

transformative style of leadership that emphasises aspects of individual consideration. This allows staff members to have a say on matters that affect them, allowing everyone to collaborate and make better, more logical decisions. When employees are treated with respect and dignity, it is simpler to keep them and they are more productive. Demonstrating a human side is a key component of academic leadership. The need to engage the people in the institution's intentions and activities will ensure that transformational programmes are effective. Regular meetings between the executive management and the Student Representative Council are recognised as one of the practises that demonstrate the institution's connection between the concerned parties. This includes strategic meetings about the institution's future as well as understanding how students conduct themselves.

Most of the leadership exerted an expression that they often allow their subordinates to adapt to change and continuously improve in their activities. This is in conjunction with the fact that they rarely are content to let others continue working in the same ways always or ask more of others than what is essential and believe that as long as things are working they do not try to change anything. However, this is also in contradiction with their idea that whatever their subordinates want to do is fine with them, since most of the leadership expressed that they rarely allow their subordinates to do whatever they want to do. The assumption in relation to the contradiction could be that the leadership require their subordinates to ask for permission before they can do whatever they want. This is to avoid a situation where subordinates perform activities that are irrelevant and not beneficial to the objectives of the institution.

The executive emphasised on the idea that a leadership that has been there long enough to see the changes and has experience understands the process better. Unlike the new leadership, which has little knowledge of the institution and has to take over from where the previous leadership left off without having sufficient knowledge of the route set by the previous leadership. The more time the leadership spends leading an institution, the more knowledge and skills they acquire about how to manage the institution. Therefore, it is empirical that they allow the leadership to be in the system long enough in order to facilitate effective transformational change.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION

The position of leading a large institution comes with a lot of authority, and the leadership has the power to exploit that influence, such as misusing the university's money and resources. It is essential that the university's leadership be not swayed by the prospect of acquiring and displaying valuables. These kinds of events and practices tend to weaken leadership. If the university is to be transformed into an institution that satisfies the needs of society and the economy of the country, the university leadership must adopt a full transformational leadership style. To strengthen the institutional structure, strategy, and values, the leadership must engage in excessive transformational activities and decision-making.

To establish where the institution wants to be in terms of leadership in academia in the future, the institution must first clearly articulate a strategy for where the university want the institution to be in a broader context, such as the role of the university in society. Only then can the university be able to define the leadership required to get there. The institution's leadership should be able to take measures to monitor and visit the various departments inside the university to gather more information from the ground up. This entails listening to the needs of students and staff, understanding the processes and methods utilised within the different departments, identifying areas for development, recognising good performance, inspiring and guiding everyone.

The leadership should guarantee that the people affected by the transformation are included in the decision-making process so that they may better comprehend the institution's objectives and vision. This will make the transformation process easier and faster since the subordinates will have a clear grasp of what is required and where to go in terms of their operations, allowing them to fulfil their duties in a way that is aligned with the vision.

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